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The project is supported by the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking and its members under grant agreement N° 101112409.

MIX-MATTERS From Waste to Wealth

In the EU, the agri-food value chain produces **113 Mt/y** of mixed-bio-waste that contains valuable compounds like polysaccharides and polyphenols compounds. However, the potential of this bio-waste as a source of recycled components remains largely untapped. Approximately **75%** of the generated bio-waste is either disposed of in landfills or incinerated. This contributes to **3%** of the total greenhouse gas emissions in the EU.

Effectively using mixed waste is challenging due to its diverse composition, including organic matter and impurities like plastic, cardboard, glass, and metal, making separating and efficiently utilising the waste difficult. Technical constraints in impurity removal and logistical challenges from scattered agents complicate the process, making valorisation less cost-effective.

MixMatters will set up the Integrated System, which involves the separation and valorisation of **3** different types of mixed bio-waste streams from the agri-food industry. These streams may contain impurities such as plastics, cardboard, or metals. The performance of the Integrated System will be demonstrated in **3** locations in Spain, specifically two in Valencia and one in the Almeria regions.

Expected impacts

Avoid landfilling/incineration of **6.240 t/y** of mixed biowaste

Recycled **1.123 t/y** of plastic

Avoid the emission of **2.780 t/y** of CO2

18 new value chains and **6 high value-added products**

MixMatters Integrated System

